

***Gasteruption erythrostomum* (Dahlbom) (Hymenoptera: Gasteruptionidae) added to the British list from Warwick Gardens, Peckham**

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Abstract

Gasteruption erythrostomum (Dahlbom) (Hymenoptera: Gasteruptionidae) is added to the British list on the basis of photographs taken by Penny Metal in Warwick Gardens, Peckham, and a specimen collected by the author.

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Paper

Gasteruption erythrostomum (Dahlbom) is added to the British list on the basis of photographs taken by Penny Metal (<https://insectinside.me>) in Warwick Gardens, Peckham on 27.vi.2015 [copyrighted figure not included], and a specimen collected by the author on 7.vii.2023.

Crosskey (1951) includes five species of *Gasteruption* in his checklist of the British evanioid wasps. Developments in synonymy aside, the checklist has remained the same since then. As accounted for by Broad and Livermore (2014), Crosskey's *G. foveolum* Szepligeti is a synonym of *G. laticeps* (Tournier). *G. pedemontanum* (Tournier) in both Crosskey's and Broad and Livermore's checklists is synonymised by van Achterberg (2013) under *G. caucasicum* (Guérin-Ménéville).

With the addition of *G. erythrostomum*, six species of the genus are now known from Britain: *G. assectator* (L.), *G. caucasicum*, *G. erythrostomum*, *G. jaculator* (L.), *G. laticeps*, and *G. minutum* (Tournier).

Females of *G. erythrostomum* are readily distinguished from those of the other known British species. The ovipositor sheath is shorter than the metasoma, but twice as long as a hind tibia or longer. This means it is longer than the ovipositor sheaths that would be found on *G. assectator* and *G. minutum*, while shorter than those which would be found on *G. caucasicum*, *G. jaculator*, and *G. laticeps*. In both sexes, *G. erythrostomum* may also be distinguishable by the combination of a wide occipital carina and a coriaceous mesoscutum. The specific epithet “erythrostomum” alludes to a further useful character: the mandibles may be orange from base to tip, where they would be black or brown in the other species.

The keys by Bogusch (2021) in English, and van Achterberg (2013) in Dutch, include the six known British species and others. The former also includes the two species, *G. boreale* (Thomson) and *G. nigritarse* (Thomson), which after the most recent checklist were excluded from synonymy with *G. minutum* and *G. assectator* by Johansson and van Achterberg (2016). In van Achterberg and Talebi (2014), *G. erythrostomum* would likely key to *G. insidiosum* Semenov.

Parslow, Schwarz, and Stevens (2020) collected host records for the known British species and others. For *G. erythrostomum*, reported hosts include *Chelostoma campanularum* (Kirby) (Megachilidae), *Hylaeus communis* Nylander, *H. hyalinatus* Smith, and *H. pectoralis* Förster (all Colletidae).

Gasteruption erythrostomum is widespread in Europe. In Czechia and Slovakia, Bogusch (2021) reports that it is recorded from June to August usually “in forest margins, forest steppes and mesic meadows.” I initially identified it as present in Warwick Gardens in Peckham, London, on the basis of photos of an ovipositing female posted by Penny Metal to the “UK Bees, Wasps and Ants” Facebook group. A further review of images from the site revealed a presence of the species there since at least 2014. I shared some of them with Kees van Achterberg, and he agreed that they were “very fine pictures” of the species. A visit to the area produced a specimen which has been deposited with the Natural History Museum. I thank Penny Metal for sharing her photos; Kees van Achterberg for reviewing their identification; BWARS for accelerating the finding of this species by their running of the Facebook group; and Chris Raper and Abigail Lowe for handling receipt of the specimen.

Author

Adam J. Roberts, King’s College London, Strand, London WC2R 2LS –
adamjroberts92@gmail.com.

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